

Education system nowadays.

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Annotation: This research is conducted with the aim of finding out the effect of education in a society. The writer would like to show how a society becomes after being facilitated to get education well, and how it is without education.

Key words: Education, Education System, School, Students

Education nowadays has become prominent thing as it involves most people to take part in this matter. In addition, it cannot be separated from human's life. Both males and females need to be educated. Education plays an important role in the development of a country. If a country does not have proper education, it may be left behind by other countries which support education. There are many factors that affect the education system. Culture, technology, and economical matters give much impact to the education system of a country. The regulation made by the government affects how the education system works in a country. The education system in Indonesia still uses the one-way communication. The teachers stand in front of in the class and explain all the materials, while the students just sit down on their seats and listen to the teachers. One-way communication has negative effects on the students. They become unconfident to share their opinions or even ask a question. The government should improve this education to a better one. Two-way communication is considered as a better way in teaching method. The development of technology contributes much impact on the education. It can be very useful for many people to get the education. Education is essential in human's life. As time goes by, system of education changes dynamically following the needs of human beings.

Education nowadays has become prominent thing as it involves most people to take part in this matter. In addition, it cannot be separated from human's life. Both males and females need to be educated. They have the same right to get education as much as they want because there is no limitation for education. No matter how old a person is, they can still take education during the rest of their lives. Hence, there is no such thing as too late to get education.

Education is the only bridge that leads people to their better futures. Education plays an important role in the development of a country. If a country does not have proper education, it may be left behind by other countries which support education. The development of a country can be determined by whether its citizens have good education or not. The better the quality of education that a country has, the faster it is likely to develop. No matter what global problems that a country is facing, whether it's the elimination of poverty, the creation of peace, or environmental energy problems, the solutions will always include education. It is never done without an education. Most people agree that education is very important in their lives. Many people compete to get better education. Many of them choose a promising institution that is considered to be the best for them to get education. The higher quality of institution they choose, the higher the educational fee they have to pay. They should spend money for education more than those for any other things. They should put education first on the list of their expenses.

Education becomes very well-known to people. Perhaps, some people cannot state the definition of education precisely, however they must have known what education is in general. Lexically, education means a process of teaching and learning to improve knowledge. The main purpose of education is to bring human beings to enlightenment, so that they know what is right and what is wrong. We must remember that intelligence is not enough. Intelligence plus character--that is the goal of true education. The complete education gives one not only power of concentration, but worthy objectives upon which to concentrate.

Generally, people get their first education since they are 3 or 4 years old. Then, they go through each level of education with their efforts. The time that they spend for getting education is not little. It often takes longer time than other activities do. Some people somehow consider education as a must-thing to have, and they cannot live without it. Hence, they can spend almost their whole lives to get education from some institutions. There are many factors that affect the education system. Culture, technology, and economical matters give much impact to the education system of a country. And also, the regulation made by the government affects how the education system works in a country. Brown and White (2013) even stressed the need for students since early childhood to become familiar with alternative practices in other countries. As time goes by, education system changes dynamically with the intention of improving it. There are many advantages and disadvantages of the change of education system. Sometimes it works well and is appropriate for the citizens of a country, and sometimes it even makes the process of educating worse. When education system does not seem to

go well, the government will propose a better one to improve it, with the consideration of some scientists and organizations involved in changing the education system. The government sometimes adopts the education system from other countries which they consider it is the best for the country. Nowadays, most students tend to focus only on their goals, whether passing a test, graduating, or getting a job that they want. They will do whatever it takes to achieve their goals quickly. However, they do not really learn what they are supposed to learn. When the students pass a test or graduate, they must have learned something that makes them succeed to achieve their goals. But, they did not really learn all the things that they should have really learned. Perhaps, they only learned how to memorize names, places, and dates, just because they wanted to pass a test, without really understanding what they were learning. Then, after the test, they will forget the materials that they have memorized, in order to clear their mind for the next test. Right now, a school is a place for most people to determine that their goal is to get out as soon as possible. The students consider that the faster they finish the school, the better it will be. They will be proud of themselves when they get a good mark in a test, or graduate with a high GPA. But, they may be afraid of what will happen next after they graduate because they realize that they have not learned the important matters that are necessary and needed when they get a job and work. In fact, many companies out there do not consider a person from how high his GPA is, but whether or not he is qualified enough to do the job that he applies. Therefore, students should really learn what is important in connection with what qualification they should have after graduation to get a job.

If the students are placed based on their divisions, they will be more confident to study because of the same level of intelligence as the other students. It is also helpful to the teachers because they will use different methods in teaching each division. When the teachers teach in a class in which the student with low intelligence are placed, they should not teach strictly, otherwise the students will blame themselves for their lack of understanding of the lesson, and also they will study passively without any interaction with the teachers. The development of technology contributes much impact on the education. The use of technical gadgets has distracted the student generation from their book study and theory oriented study. Hence, educational institution should embrace technology to enhance their education pattern and teaching methods. Technologies can be very useful for many people to get the education. It makes the process of obtaining knowledge easier. For example, the use of the Internet enables people to search and share anything, so we can obtain much information that we would like to have.

However, it somehow has disadvantages that can worsen the process of educating. For example, students nowadays do not get used to writing the materials that they are learning in classroom. They become lazy to write because they are used to typing anything on their laptops that is considered much faster than writing it.

In conclusion, education is essential in human's life. As time goes by, system of education changes dynamically following the needs of human beings. There are still many things that need to be improved in order to get a good system of education. Therefore, all of the people need to be involved in improving it, so that the education system gets better and better every year. The main factor is how good the facilitation given by the local government to get education is.

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